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Impact Factor 2.30

Projects Resource Mobilization and Performance of the National Agricultural and Rural Inclusive Growth Program in Kenya

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Abstract

County Government projects face problems despite their great importance in supporting the provision of people's livelihoods and the development of the national economy. Over the years, County governments in Kenya have implemented various development projects such as National Agricultural and Rural Inclusive Growth Program (NARIGP). Most county governments implementing NARIGP are reported not to have delivered significant development impacts, with 12% complete, 15% ongoing projects, 67% stalled, and 6% abandoned. Most of the projects under NARIGP have faced challenges related to poor implementation practices. The study aims to assess the influence of project resource mobilization on the performance of the NARIGP in Kenya. The study adopted an explanatory research design targeting a population of 229 respondents comprising project managers, project sponsors, and community members. The study used stratified sampling; the study utilized structured to collect data. The questionnaires were distributed via google forms to collect data for the research and to enhance the questionnaire's validity and reliability; a pilot study was carried out in Kiminini sub-county. Quantitative data were coded and entered into the Statistical Package for Social Scientists (SPSS, Version 27.0) and analyzed using descriptive statistics. The findings indicate a positive effect of resource mobilization on the performance of the NARIGP. Based on this conclusion, effective resource mobilization is essential for the project's success. To achieve this, a concerted effort is required to enhance resource mobilization strategies, which include the effective identification of necessary resources for project implementation, such as budgets, equipment, and personnel. A focused approach to improving resource identification should involve implementing systematic methods to accurately pinpoint all required resources. By doing so, project planning and execution will be more comprehensive and effective. Additionally, it is crucial to strengthen collaboration with stakeholders. Building robust partnerships will facilitate the exploration of additional resources, support, and expertise, thereby enhancing the overall capacity of the project. This collaborative effort not only enriches the resource pool but also fosters a more engaged community, ultimately contributing to the successful implementation and sustainability of the NARIGP

Keywords: Project Resource Mobilization, Performance, NARIGP, Project

1. Introduction

Projects are designed with a defined budget, limited resources, and deadlines. A particular quantity of financial, material, and human resources is used during specific periods. Nevertheless, resources and time are frequently in short supply. The primary goal of a project is to maximize the utilization of available resources and time to have the greatest potential impact in resolving the problem and bringing about positive change. This principle is the foundation of project management in all businesses (Chaplowe and Cousins, 2015). Finally, the goal of

making the best use of limited resources and time limitations provides the basis for project planning in all organizations, including cooperatives. Obtaining more significant resources and seeking additional money is essential to solve the underlying issue. A resource plan specifies the requirements and costs for all necessary inputs, such as personnel, office space or facilities, equipment, materials, or services, such as specific subcontracting supplies, training sessions, and other diverse inputs (Ogunde et al., 2017).

The results-based management strategy entails creating a resource program based on the tasks listed in the organizational breakdown matrix and calendar. A list of required inputs for each activity is established and then classified (e.g., equipment, personnel, raw materials) to create a strategic procurement strategy for the project. The resources required to carry out the actions associated with each outcome should be stated. Estimating the required resources for each sub-activity in the performance management process is usually unnecessary. Resource mobilization encompasses all of the necessary measures to acquire newly found resources inside an organization and enhance the usage of existing resources to raise the total number of resources. Ogunde et al. (2017) state that resource mobilization is essential for organizational strengthening.

Sadly, donor resource rivalry is fierce, and an institution's capacity to obtain these resources depends on the amount of competitiveness in their area and their capacity to uncover new sources of resources within their surroundings (Marleand Vidal, 2016). Most groups are unsure whether funders would stop sponsoring their programs and redirect the cash to other critical needs. Also, contributors may be unable to offer resources in some cases, particularly if their firm is deteriorating. These circumstances create donor financial unpredictability, making it difficult for institutions to successfully run and administer their operations.

According to Chaplowe and Cousins (2015), creating a resource mobilization plan or strategy can enable the company to use its resources that are easily accessible nearby to help the company. Investigating alternative financing sources may increase program adaptability and self-sufficiency while decreasing dependency on foreign or donor funds. As competitiveness for grant funding intensifies, institutions can manage financial constraints and successfully execute projects by exploring alternate choices and mobilizing diverse resource flows (Marleand Vidal, 2016).

According to Chaplowe and Cousins (2015), good project management depends on efficient resource mobilization, scheduling, and optimization. Priorities ascribed to project activities dictate the distribution of limited resources, which may be estimated using project time effectively and intuitive analysis. When resources are limited, the goal is to develop an adequate timetable feasible, minimizing project length while optimizing resource use (Meridith et al., 2008). Because resources are few and costly, they must be utilized effectively and efficiently to guarantee a successful project. Yet, resource competitiveness is increasing as the variety of development players grows, and resources become scarce due to the recent worldwide financial crisis. As a result, resource mobilization can substantially impact project success.

According to Kerzner (2015), optimal project management methods such projects resource mobilization may increase corporate value, improve benefits realization, and improve benefits management operations. According to Badewi (2016), project management methods are critical for success. Effective project management strategies can increase the chance of project success (Thomas and Mullaly, 2018). Nonetheless, businesses must assess the relevance of each practice, as its influence may differ between enterprises. To effectively execute project management practices, tools and processes must be tailored to the unique environment of the company (Tereso et al., 2019).

According to Singh, Chandurkar, and Dutt (2017), a significant concern is the lack of resource mobilization, which is crucial for enhancing project performance. Minyiri and Muchelule (2018) further emphasize that many projects fail primarily due to inadequate financial resources, which are often insufficient to support successful

project outcomes. In Kenya, County Government projects struggle with insufficient resources, despite their vital role in supporting both people's livelihoods and the national economy (Ong'era and Musili, 2019). The Info-Track report (2015) indicates that while Kenyan counties have implemented various development projects over the past four years, many are ranked highly among the 47 counties for having executed prominent initiatives. However, a recent study by the World Bank (2021) reveals that most counties engaged in the National Agricultural and Rural Inclusive Growth Program (NARIGP) have not delivered significant development projects to the public, with a staggering 57% reporting a shortage of resources. This situation correlates with a 47% project failure rate across the country. Despite these challenges, there remains a critical gap in studies focused on project resource mobilization within the NARIGP and its impact on project performance. Therefore, the main objective of this study is to investigate the influence of project resource mobilization on the performance of the National Agricultural and Rural Inclusive Growth Program in Kenya.

2. Theoretical Review

This research was guided by Resource-Based View Theory. Resource-based view Theory (RBVT) is a standard project management theory that examines how resources may be exploited to obtain a competitive advantage. According to Kraaijenbrink et al. (2010), the Resource-based view theory has achieved significant acceptance in project management due to its understandable core message, quick face validity, and simplicity of training. Similarly, Almarri and Gardiner (2014) argue that the RBV theory of the firm, a strategic management theory, is commonly used by project managers to achieve competitive advantage through the utilization of assets, including project management (PM) capabilities that are customized to an organization's specific requirements and improved over the years. As indicated by their research in four different businesses, Killen et al. (2012) discovered that strategy formulation theories such as RBV can effectively promote study results in project management.

According to Mansour et al. (2022), RBV theory has received widespread recognition as a critical theory due to its potential to deliver strategic and organizational insights into a firm's competitive edge. RBV is used in project management to discover PM resources that drive a firm's competitive advantage. According to the study's author, RBV has played an essential role in defining enterprises' strategic and organizational concerns over the last several decades, offering a framework for maximizing a firm's potential by building key links between its resources. It was also the first theory to understand that project management resources might be used to gain a competitive advantage. As a result, Alameri (2018) underlines the significance of RBV continuing to make a difference in the achievement of both the management of projects and their execution and organizations. However, critics have raised concerns about the theory's emphasis on centrality as a significant research concept. They propose that there should be a clear distinction between core and peripheral units and their functions within an organization (Ashar and Shapiro, 1988).

The resource allocation theory is important for understanding how mobilized resources are to project supervision and assessment and top management's influence in mobilizing resources to project performance. This theory informs independent variable mobilization. Resource-based Theory is considered relevant for this study to understand the effect of Resource Mobilization on the performance of the national agricultural, rural inclusive project in Kenya; hence it provides a theoretical background.

2.1 Empirical Review

Ronoh and Kirui (2021) investigated how resource scheduling influences the performance of housing building projects in Nairobi, Kenya. They chose 79 private residential building projects using essential random selection and selective sampling approaches. Project managers, supervisors, and contractors from each selected project participated in the study. The researchers used questionnaires to collect data, which they then analyzed

using descriptive and inferential statistics. The study revealed a substantial relationship between resource scheduling and performance outcomes.

Makokha and Ngugi (2022) investigated how the allocation of resources impacts the Busia County Government's execution of healthcare programs in Kenya. They employed a descriptive study technique, concentrating on six Busia County Government health programs. The study's participants were project managers and team members, with 95 respondents questioned by a census. The researchers utilized the questionnaires. They also employed inferential statistics like correlation and regression analysis to discover how one variable affected another. The study found that resource allocation had a favorable and significant influence on the Busia County Government's project implementation in Kenya.

Rugiri and Njangiru (2018) performed research in Nyeri County, Kenya, to investigate the influence of the allocation of resources on the success of water projects supported by the CDF. Using a random stratified sampling approach, the researchers chose Sixty project teams for the study. To uncover essential findings, they used correlation and regression analytics, multivariate analysis, and multivariate techniques to evaluate the data. The regression analysis findings showed that available resources were an essential determinant of project performance, and the Pearson product-moment correlation investigation discovered a positive association between resource distribution and project outcomes.

Mwinyimkuu and Mokaya (2018) studied Sustainability of Community-Based Armyworm Forecasting in Moshi District, Kilimanjaro Region, Tanzania. The target population comprised of 290 farmers in Moshi district, Kilimanjaro region. Stratified random sampling was used to select a sample of 169 from the population. A researcher's self-developed questionnaire was used as a data collection tool. Findings from linear multiple regression established significant positive correlations between financial resources and sustainability of CBAF.

Obegi and Kimutai (2017) investigated the influence of resource scheduling on the effectiveness of NGO projects in Nairobi City County. They discovered that effective resource scheduling is a critical determinant of project performance. The study found frequent budgetary control, comparing spending to project budgets, project adjustments throughout implementation, well-equipped project employees, and periodic project performance reviews were essential to project success. Resource scheduling was important in project performance because it ensured that projects stayed under budget, modifications were made to suit changing demands, and project workers had the resources to execute their jobs.

Pinha and Ahluwalia (2019) investigated the effect of optimized resource management on the duration and costs of projects. They discovered that inadequate resource management is frequently the root cause of cost overruns and project delays. To solve this issue, they devised a method that allows project managers to examine several possibilities to lower the project's cost and time. The researchers pioneered a novel approach to flexible allocation of resources and program management, which is critical in today's project scheduling systems. They found that as project settings get more complex, cutting-edge techniques to project scheduling should indeed be employed to ensure the optimal success of a project.

Ndayisaba and Mulyungi (2018) studied resource management in implementing the Project to Improve Livelihoods in Rural Rwanda. They studied the distribution of time, money, and human resources and involved all stakeholders. They examined how the variables they researched were interrelated using quantitative approaches, notably regression analysis. They discovered that resource management had a significant influence on the successful completion of a project, contributing to 83.7% of its accomplishment in the Muhanga district of rural Rwanda (Ndayisaba and Mulyungi,2018)

3.0 Research Methodology

The study's conceptual foundation is based on the Positivist philosophy, which is seen to help understand the problems that impact project success in Kenya. This study used an explanatory analysis design to demonstrate the causal effect link rather than just describing the events under investigation (Gratton and Jones, 2010).

3.1 Target Population and sampling

The study focused on a target population of 229 respondents, comprising various accounting officers involved in the National Agricultural and Rural Inclusive Growth Project (NARIGP) in Kenya. This group included County Project Coordinators, agricultural component leaders, community-driven leaders, line project managers, finance officers, project donors, the National Project Coordinator, and Directors of Supply Chain Management. These individuals are directly benefiting from 20 ongoing micro-projects across 21 counties in sectors such as agriculture, livestock, fisheries, irrigation, cooperative development, crop development, water and environment, land and physical planning, and public works (Kothari, 2011). From this target population, a sample size of 146 was determined, using a simple random sampling method to select respondents.

3.2 Data Collection instruments and Procedure

The study used structured questionnaires to collect both quantitative and qualitative data. The questionnaires were administered to the sampled respondents concerning their responsibilities in the agriculture sector. A Likert scale in the questionnaire was employed where most questions were structured on an agreement continuum using a 5-point Likert-type scale. The mixed questionnaires are presented on a Likert scale, with a score of 1-5, tabulated as follows: 1= Strongly Disagree; 2= Disagree; 3= Somewhat Agree; 4= Agree; 5=Strongly Agree. A pilot study was conducted to check the accuracy and appropriateness of the research design and instruments. The aim is to make sure that the questionnaire is consistent, clear, and can be understood. The questionnaire was piloted using 15 respondents drawn from the target population. Mugenda (2003) asserts that 10% of the sample population is adequate for piloting. The validity and reliability of the research tool were also determined. Face validity was applied in the early phases of designing the questionnaire. Face validity was attained by supervisors critiquing the questionnaire. Experts examining the items give their opinions, and necessary adjustments were made to fit their purpose. According to Middleton (2020), face validity reflects how appropriate the content of a test is on the surface or face of it if the content of the test appears to be suitable to its stated aims. The study was evaluated for content validity using the Content Validity Index (CVI). According to Polit and Beck (2011), a content validity index with at least six experts should give a maximum CVI of 0.8. Further, construct validity was used to validate the instruments. Construct validity is when a tool or test can measure what it is intended to measure. Cronbach's alpha coefficient was calculated to determine the correlation between different items under study.

3.3 Data Analysis and Model specification

The primary raw data was obtained from the questionnaires and checked for omissions, legibility, and consistency before being coded for analysis. The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 27 was used to analyze quantitative and inferential statistics. The inferential analysis was used in examining the association between project resource mobilization and the performance of NARIGIP in Kenya. The regression model adopted was;

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \varepsilon + Z$$

Where: Y = performance of NARIGIP, X_1 = project resource mobilization, β_0 is a constant (in which the value of the dependent variable is; Y when all the independent variables are 0), β_1 is the regression coefficients or change induced by independent. ε : The error term.

4.0 Results and Discussions

This section presents the findings and results of the use of variables using procedures mentioned in chapter three of the methodology. 125 of the 146 surveys that were distributed were completed and returned, accounting for 85.61% of the responses. Mugenda and Mugenda (2003) state that a response rate of 50% is deemed appropriate, a rate of 60% is good, and a rate of 70% or higher is seen very good.

4.1 Descriptive statistics

The descriptive statistics related to resource mobilization present a nuanced view of the project's effectiveness across various facets of resource management. The assessment of necessary resource identification received a moderately positive evaluation (Mean = 3.46, Std. Dev = 1.42), yet the relatively high standard deviation suggests considerable variability in respondents' confidence levels. Similarly, perceptions of adequate resource allocation indicate a moderate level of sufficiency for successful project execution (Mean = 3.14, Std. Dev = 1.43), bringing to light potential concerns about overall adequacy. Conversely, the mechanisms established for acquiring and mobilizing required resources garnered a less favorable response (Mean = 2.95, Std. Dev = 1.26), highlighting respondents' belief that there is significant room for improvement in these processes. In terms of monitoring and managing resource utilization, results showed some effectiveness (Mean = 3.14, Std. Dev = 1.41), while proactive identification of resource gaps received a moderate score (Mean = 3.10, Std. Dev = 1.50). Collaboration with stakeholders was viewed more positively (Mean = 3.44, Std. Dev = 1.44), showcasing effective efforts to leverage additional resources. However, the overall resource mobilization score of 2.94 (Mean = 2.94, Std. Dev = 0.76) underscores significant challenges within the mobilization processes, indicating an urgent need for enhancement. These findings highlight the necessity for refining resource allocation strategies and fostering stronger collaboration with stakeholders to ensure effective mobilization and utilization of resources, ultimately improving project performance.

Table 1 Descriptive statistics for Resource Mobilization

	Mean	Std. Dev
The project team has effectively identified the resources required for project implementation (such as budget, equipment, and personnel).	3.46	1.42
Adequate resources have been allocated to the project to ensure its successful execution.	3.14	1.43
The project team has established precise mechanisms for acquiring and mobilizing the required resources.	2.95	1.26
The project team actively monitors and manages resource utilization to ensure efficient and effective use.	3.14	1.41
The project team proactively identifies and addresses any resource gaps or constraints that may impact project progress.	3.10	1.50
The project team collaborates with relevant stakeholders to leverage additional resources and support when needed.	3.44	1.44
The project team has a well-defined plan for resource allocation and prioritization.	3.16	1.47
Resource Mobilization	2.94	0.76

The descriptive statistics summarized in Table 2 provide valuable insights into the performance of the National Agricultural and Rural Inclusive Growth Project (NARIGP). Each performance indicator reveals different facets of project execution, reflecting the respondents' sentiments regarding its success. The findings indicate that respondents perceive the project as having somewhat met its intended aims (Mean = 2.94, Std. Dev = 1.32), stayed within budget (Mean = 2.85, Std. Dev = 1.41), and delivered quality outputs (Mean = 2.86, Std. Dev = 1.44). The significant standard deviations imply that experiences related to these aspects varied markedly among stakeholders, suggesting that some may have encountered severe budget constraints or quality issues, while others had a more satisfactory experience.

In terms of stakeholder expectations, the findings show that the project outcomes have largely failed to meet the anticipations of those involved (Mean = 2.82, Std. Dev = 1.37). This reinforces a sense of disappointment among respondents, and the variability in responses indicates that specific groups may feel particularly let down by the project's results. On a more positive note, the project received a higher mean score (Mean = 3.46, Std. Dev = 1.39) for its effectiveness in addressing identified risks and issues, suggesting that risk management is perceived as a relative success. However, the high standard deviation indicates that while some stakeholders recognize effective risk management, others may have had negative experiences or perceptions. The indicator reflecting the project's ability to generate positive impacts has the highest mean (Mean = 3.59, Std. Dev = 1.40), suggesting that respondents generally see value in the benefits provided to both the organization and the wider community. Nevertheless, similar to other indicators, the high standard deviation indicates that this perception is not uniform across all stakeholders. Lastly, the overall performance score (Mean = 3.07, Std. Dev = 0.75), which sits just above the midpoint, suggests a mixed but generally positive perception of NARIGP's effectiveness. The lower standard deviation compared to individual metrics suggests greater consensus among respondents regarding overall performance, even as specific areas show considerable variation in satisfaction. In conclusion, while NARIGP demonstrates strengths in risk management and perceived positive impacts, significant challenges remain regarding goal achievement, budget adherence, and stakeholder satisfaction.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics for NARIGP performance

	Mean	Std. Dev
The project has achieved its intended goals and objectives.	2.94	1.32
The project was completed within the allocated time frame.	3.07	1.43
The project was completed within the allocated budget.	2.85	1.41
The project deliverables meet the desired quality standards.	2.86	1.44
The project outcomes have met or exceeded stakeholders' expectations.	2.82	1.37
The project has effectively addressed identified risks and issues.	3.46	1.39
The project has generated positive impacts or benefits for the organization or community.	3.53	1.40
NARIGP performance	3.07	0.75

4.2 Correlation Analysis

The correlation analysis results between NARIGP performance and resource mobilization demonstrate a significant and strong positive relationship ($r = 0.673$, $p = 0.000$). This suggests that as efforts in resource mobilization increase, the performance of the NARIGP also improves correspondingly. The robust correlation indicates that effective resource mobilization is pivotal for enhancing project outcomes. This finding highlights the need for further investigation through regression analysis to explore the nature of this relationship in greater depth and to understand how resource mobilization contributes to the overall success of the NARIGP.

Table 3: Correlation Analysis

		NARIGP performance	Resource Mobilization
NARIGP performance	Pearson Correlation	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)		
	N	125	
Resource Mobilization	Pearson Correlation	.673**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	
	N	125	125

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

4.3 Regression Analysis

The regression analysis presented in Table 4 offers significant insights into the relationship between resource mobilization and the performance of NARIGP. The R-squared value of 0.452 indicates that approximately 45.2% of the variance in NARIGP performance can be accounted for by resource mobilization, highlighting a moderately strong explanatory power for the model. This suggests that resource mobilization is a crucial factor influencing project performance. Furthermore, the ANOVA results support this assertion, showing that the overall model significantly predicts NARIGP performance, with an F-value of 101.644 and a significance level of 0.000. These findings imply that the regression model is a good fit for the data and provides robust evidence of a statistically significant relationship between resource mobilization and project performance.

The regression coefficients reveal the extent of effect resource mobilization has on NARIGP performance, with a β coefficient of 0.663 ($p = 0.000$, which is less than 0.050). This indicates that for every one-unit increase in resource mobilization, there is a corresponding increase of 0.663 units in NARIGP performance, holding other factors constant. The standardized coefficient (Beta) of 0.673 reinforces this assertion, pointing to a strong positive relationship between resource mobilization and project performance. This relationship underscores the notion that effective resource mobilization is integral to enhancing the success of the NARIGP. This finding is consistent with the work of Ronoh and Kirui (2021), who revealed a substantial relationship between resource scheduling and project performance outcomes, emphasizing the importance of aligned resource management in achieving project goals. Similarly, Makokha and Ngugi (2022) reported that resource allocation had a favorable and significant influence on project implementation for the Busia County Government in Kenya, reinforcing the vital role of strategic resource management in local governance projects. Furthermore, Rugiri and Njangiru (2018) demonstrated that available resources are essential determinants of project performance, establishing a clear connection between resource management practices and successful project execution. The relevance of resource scheduling is further highlighted by Obegi and Kimutai (2017), who noted that effective resource scheduling is crucial for ensuring projects remain within budget and can adapt to changing demands, thereby equipping project teams with the necessary resources to perform their tasks. In an increasingly complex project environment, Pinha and Ahluwalia (2019) advocate for the use of advanced scheduling techniques to optimize project success. Moreover, Ndayisaba and Mulyungi (2018) discovered that effective resource management significantly influenced project completion success, accounting for an impressive 83.7% of project accomplishment in the Muhanga district of rural Rwanda.

Table 4: Regression analysis

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	1.126	0.199		5.647	0.000
Resource Mobilization	0.663	0.066	0.673	10.082	0.000
Model Summary Statistics					
R	0.673				
R Square	0.452				
Adjusted R Square	0.448				
ANOVA for goodness of fit)					
F	101.644				
Sig.	0.000				

a Dependent Variable: NARIGP performance

4.4 Conclusions and Recommendations

Based in conclusion, effective resource mobilization is essential for the successful performance of the National Agricultural and Rural Inclusive Growth Project (NARIGP). This necessitates a concerted effort to increase resource mobilization, which includes the effective identification of necessary resources for project

implementation, such as budgets, equipment, and personnel. Moreover, the collaboration with relevant stakeholders is vital for leveraging additional resources and support when needed. A well-defined plan for resource allocation and prioritization, along with active monitoring and management of resource utilization, ensures that resources are used efficiently and effectively. However, significant improvements are still required in establishing precise mechanisms for acquiring and mobilizing the required resources, as well as in identifying and addressing any resource gaps or constraints that may hinder project progress.

To enhance resource mobilization and improve the performance of the NARIGP, several recommendations are proposed. First, there should be a focus on enhancing resource identification by implementing systematic methods to pinpoint all necessary resources, including budgets, equipment, and personnel. This comprehensive approach will ensure that project planning and execution are thorough and effective. Second, strengthening collaboration with stakeholders is critical. Building stronger partnerships can facilitate exploration of additional resources, support, and expertise. Regular stakeholder meetings and collaborative workshops can bolster this engagement and create a more integrated support network. Additionally, developing comprehensive resource allocation plans is essential. Creating detailed and structured plans for resource allocation and prioritization can guide the efficient use of available resources and ensure that every project phase is properly supported. Furthermore, establishing robust resource mobilization mechanisms will streamline the process of acquiring and mobilizing resources. Clear protocols outlining the necessary steps and responsibilities will help reduce delays and inefficiencies in resource utilization.

5.0 Areas of Further Research

This study focused specifically on NARIGP within the agricultural sector, which may limit the generalizability of findings related to resource mobilization. Future research should consider extending the scope to include not just resource mobilization, but also other critical project management practices, such as strategic planning and risk management. These additional dimensions could provide a more comprehensive understanding of the factors that contribute to project success in various sectors. Moreover, the current study relied primarily on subjective measures, which are inherently tied to respondents' perceptions and may introduce biases. To enhance the robustness of future investigations, it is recommended that researchers incorporate objective measures alongside subjective assessments. This dual approach can provide a more balanced and accurate evaluation of resource mobilization and its impact on project performance. By diversifying the focus and methodologies used in future studies, researchers can capture a more holistic view of the dynamics at play within project management practices and their effects across different context

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